

USE OF HORN/LENS ANTENNAS FOR FREE-SPACE MICROWAVE PERMITTIVITY MEASUREMENTS

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Abstract: Measurements of the dielectric properties of wheat at microwave frequencies were performed in free space using a pair of horn/lens antennas. Undesirable effects such as mismatches, multiple reflections and diffraction at the edges of the samples were minimized by selecting optimum conditions and the use of a focused beam. Results are shown at 24 °C for samples of different moisture content and bulk density.

INTRODUCTION

Measurement of the dielectric properties of materials is a fundamental step in the design of reliable nondestructive sensors for determining physical properties of materials in the food, agricultural, pharmaceutical, construction and other industries. This is mainly because of their intrinsic nature and their dependence, at a given frequency, on entities such as, temperature, moisture content, density, and composition [1]. However, for their effective use to determine indirectly these entities, two important tasks have to be addressed. First, the accuracy with which the dielectric properties can be measured and secondly the identification, theoretically or empirically, of appropriate relationships between these properties and the desired entity. Particulate materials are random dense media for which theoretical electromagnetic analysis is somewhat complex and an exact derivation of their constitutive properties is difficult [2]. Therefore, the experimental approach is the only alternative for quantifying these properties, and in many practical instances, provides satisfactory results. Free space techniques [3] have the advantage of being nondestructive, contactless, and most often not requiring any special sample preparation. Therefore, they are suitable for continuous monitoring and control which is a valuable feature in highly automated industries. A free-space transmission microwave technique was developed to determine the dielectric properties of wheat at room temperature, 24 °C, over a wide range of frequency, 4 to 12 GHz, and practical ranges of moisture content and bulk density. In free-space measurements, errors are often caused by mismatches, multiple reflections, diffraction at the sample edges and parasitic interference from the immediate environment. To eliminate multiple reflections within the sample, appropriate thickness can be selected. The remaining effects were minimized by using a pair of horn/lens antennas providing a microwave focused beam and by applying time-domain gating. The experimental design is reported along with the variation of the dielectric properties with frequency, bulk density and moisture content.

THEORY

The relative complex permittivity ϵ is defined as $\epsilon = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$, where ϵ' is the dielectric constant and ϵ'' is the loss factor. In fact, for a material such as wheat, the relative complex permittivity is the effective permittivity of the air-kernel mixture. Consider a slab of dielectric material of thickness d in free space. The material has a bulk density ρ , a moisture content M and a temperature T . The bulk density in kg/m^3 is defined, on a gravimetric basis, as $\rho = \frac{m_w + m_d}{v}$, where m_w , m_d , and v are

the mass of water, mass of dry material and total volume respectively. The moisture content in percent is defined, on a wet basis, as $M = \frac{m_w}{m_w + m_d} \times 100$. For a linearly polarized, uniform plane

wave, normally incident on the dielectric slab, the transmission coefficient is expressed as

$$\tau = \frac{(1 - \Gamma^2)e^{-\gamma d}}{1 - \Gamma^2 e^{-2\gamma d}} \quad (1)$$

where Γ is the reflection coefficient at the air-slab interface, given by $\Gamma = (1 - \sqrt{\epsilon}) / (1 + \sqrt{\epsilon})$, and γ is the complex propagation constant defined as, $\gamma = \alpha + j\beta = j(2\pi/\lambda_0)\sqrt{\epsilon}$, where α is the attenuation constant, β is the phase constant and λ_0 is the free-space wavelength. For low loss-materials, $\epsilon'' \ll \epsilon'$, the two components of the relative complex permittivity may be approximated by

$$\epsilon' = (\beta/\beta_0)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon'' = 2\alpha\beta/\beta_0^2 \quad (3)$$

where β_0 is the phase constant for free-space wavelength λ_0 , and $\beta_0 = 2\pi/\lambda_0$. Both α and β can be determined experimentally by measurements of the attenuation A and the phase shift ϕ introduced by the slab.

PERMITTIVITY MEASUREMENTS

The measurement setup consists of two linearly polarized, ultra wideband horn/lens antennas (2 to 21 GHz), AEL¹ model AHO-2077/L, connected with high quality coaxial cables to the S-parameter test set of the Hewlett-Packard 8510B vector network analyzer (VNA). The antennas were mounted 61-cm apart on a stable fixture which kept them well aligned. The horn/lens antennas collimate the electromagnetic energy in a relatively small beam and provide a plane wave at short distance from the transmitting antenna. These features allow the measuring system to be compact, reduce the size of the sample required, and minimize the diffraction effects at the edges of the sample. The first measurement tests were made by placing a square planar sheet of Rexolite 1422 (31cm x 31 cm) 2.0 cm thick, perpendicular to the focused beam, between the transmitting and the receiving antenna. The VNA was calibrated in the transmission mode (response calibration) between 2 and 13 GHz and an appropriate time-domain gating was applied so that the gated frequency-domain response was a good average of the ungated response. From measurements of the attenuation A and the phase shift ϕ introduced by the planar sheet, the dielectric constant and loss factor were calculated according to (2) and (3) with $\alpha = A/d$ and $\beta = \phi/d + \beta_0$. Measurements performed at different distances from the transmitting antenna provided reasonable values for the dielectric constant. At a midband frequency of 8 GHz the values were 2.527, 2.519 and 2.521 for distances of 14, 30.6 and 48.5 cm, respectively. This agrees well with the known value of 2.53 at 2.45 to 22.0 GHz, [5]. However, the loss factor was of poor accuracy. This is to be expected as the free-space methods are known to be inaccurate for very low loss material, $\epsilon''/\epsilon' < 0.1$ [3]. For wheat permittivity measurements, a sample holder, made of 2.5-cm-thick Styrofoam sheet ($\epsilon' = 1.03$) with a rectangular cross section, was filled with kernels and placed between the two antennas. In this way a dense layer of randomly oriented kernels is exposed to the incident beam. The dimensions of the layer were 26 cm transverse, 26.15 cm in height and 10.95 cm in thickness. The thickness was selected to ensure a 10-dB one-way attenuation through the sample which avoids multiple reflection problems inside the sample. To verify the uniformity of the plane wave between the antennas, measurements of A and ϕ were performed at different locations for a sample of average moisture content and average bulk density. The references for attenuation and phase shift were set with a response type calibration and the empty sample holder between the antennas. The sample was first placed at exactly midway, 0-cm position, and then moved away or towards the transmitting antennas along the propagation axis. Both A and ϕ were position independent. Wheat samples for measurements were placed exactly midway with the first interface at 25.025 cm from the transmitting antenna. At this distance, the E-plane 3-dB and 10-dB beamwidths at 8 GHz were 4.65 cm and 8.28 cm, respectively, based on

¹ Mention of company or trade names is for purpose of description only and does not imply endorsement by the U. S. Department of Agriculture. Provision of the antennas by Tracor Aerospace Electronic Systems, Inc., for this research is gratefully acknowledged.

the radiation pattern provided by the manufacturer. To minimize the diffraction effects at the edges of the sample, the transverse and height dimensions were selected to meet the criterion of three times the E-plane 3-dB beamwidth [3] over the whole frequency range. Samples of wheat with moisture content ranging from 11.2% to 18.5%, wet basis, were prepared. Attenuation and phase shift were measured for each sample at three different densities, ranging from loosely packed to tightly packed, at ten frequencies between 4 and 12 GHz. The gate parameters were selected after several trials with different samples and comparison of the gated and ungated response in the frequency domain. Because the thickness d is greater than the wavelength in the sample material, an ambiguity in phase shift occurs. Therefore,

$$\phi = \varphi - 2\pi n \quad (4)$$

where φ is the reading of the VNA, $-\pi \leq \varphi \leq +\pi$, and n is an integer to be determined. The integer can be determined either by repeating the measurements with samples of different thickness or by taking measurements at two frequencies [4].

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Variations of ϵ' and ϵ'' with frequency, bulk density and moisture content are shown in figures 1, 2 and 3. The dielectric constant ϵ' slightly decreases with frequency while the loss factor ϵ'' does not exhibit any change with frequency (see Fig. 1). Both ϵ' and ϵ'' increase quadratically with ρ (Fig. 2) and have higher values at lower frequencies. Fig. 3 illustrates variations of ϵ'/ρ and ϵ''/ρ with moisture content at 24 °C and different frequencies. For each moisture content only the medium bulk density is shown. Dividing by ρ eliminates the residual density effect. Both ϵ'/ρ and ϵ''/ρ increase quadratically with moisture content with higher values at lower frequencies.

A microwave free-space transmission method using a focused beam was developed for accurate measurements of the complex permittivity. The permittivity can be used effectively to predict nondestructively and continuously physical entities such as bulk density and moisture content of a given material if appropriate correlations are identified. Although, the complex permittivity shows little variation with frequency, measurements at lower frequencies have the advantage of being less affected by scattering which can be expected, in some instances, to increase the measured value of ϵ'' . Bulk density and moisture content affect in a similar way the two components of the complex permittivity. Therefore, when ϵ' and ϵ'' are used to predict either entity at a given frequency and temperature, their effects have to be decoupled. Recently, a method based on permittivity measurements at microwave frequencies [6] was developed for simultaneous and independent determination of bulk density and moisture content. The accuracy with which these entities can be predicted is critically based upon the accuracy with which ϵ' and ϵ'' are determined, and, thus in this instance, on the accuracy with which the attenuation and phase shift are measured. Repeatability measurements (ten measurements) on a sample of average moisture content (14.24%) and medium bulk density (811 kg/m³) have shown that the attenuation and phase shift errors are less than 0.05 dB and 0.44 °, respectively.

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Fig. 1. Complex permittivity of hard red winter wheat as a function of frequency at 24 °C. Sample: $M=14.24\%$, $\rho=811 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Fig. 2. Complex permittivity of hard red winter wheat as a function of bulk density at indicated frequencies and 24 °C. $M=14.24\%$.

Fig. 3. Complex permittivity divided by bulk density of hard red winter wheat as a function of moisture content at indicated frequencies and 24 °C.